

LEARNING TO WORKING WITHIN A GROUP AND SHARPENING COLLABORATIVE SKILLS

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Abstract: This article is about combination of teamwork and collaborative encouraging to employees feel valued, safe, comfortable, and flush with opportunity for growth by teamwork. Furthermore, territory where groups of each single person can execute aims through powerful skills as well as efficacious work. Collaborative teamwork can foster upheaval, increase job contentment, find solutions to settle troubles and evolve superb career attributes. This article is devoted to what teamwork and collaborative are, ways to learning, as well as improving collaboration and teamwork and also well-beings of using both of them.

Key words: working, group, sharpening, collaborative skills, ways to learning, soft skills, improving, analyzing, discussion, comprehension, individuals.

Introduction

Group work is a collaborative effort among some people to accomplish a task. Group work can have positive effects on both groups, and individuals within them. People are different in many ways. Research shows that collaborative critical thinking leads to better outcomes. People are more likely to take calculated risks that lead to innovation if they have the support of a team behind them. Working in a team encourages personal growth, job satisfaction, and reduces stress. Collaborative skills are to work with others efficiently. In this workplace, collaborating means anything from analyzing new ideas with a colleague to brainstorm with a customer collaboration skills are one of the top character traits, patrons want from their workers 6 major collaboration skills and also how to promote them.

Broad-mindedness is one of the most crucial aspects which is being opened to and accepting of creative spirit.

2. Able to convey thoughts easily.
3. Operation.
4. Abiding.
5. Flexibility
6. Discussion of issues.

Main parts

Here are great many ideas how to learning to work within a group. One of the most or significant things is aim. Aim can be considered essential tool to work in a group. People in teams are working towards a common goal. Moreover, each person should be honest or within a team everyone should also get their duties. Positive Mindset, time-management play an important role to accomplish tasks. Establish group rules, and goals. Mainly, if they do not complain about anything. It can organize as a perfect group. Learning to work within a group is different due to differentiates of learner's ages and characteristics of young and olds. At this moment, collaborative skills are crucial at the process of working within a group. Being able to communicate thoughts and feelings clearly, listening attentively, owning up themselves errors and appreciating the unique perspectives of coworkers. True teamwork involves combining the efforts of each team member to reach a shared objective. Method of working in groups is a creative work in the lesson that is aimed at learning the educational material or completing the assigned task by dividing them into groups in order to activate the learners. When using the method of working in groups, the teacher has the opportunity to save time compared to other interactive methods. Because the teacher can engage and assess all learners at the same time.

Advantages of working within groups:

1. It leads to better mastering of the teaching content.
2. To improve interaction skills.
3. There is an opportunity to time-saving.

4. Self and inter-group assessment will be available.

When creative research is organized in groups, the educational material to be studied at the lesson is divided into small parts. Then, assignments on these parts are distributed to each learner. As a result, each learner contributes to the completion of the Common task. A discussion on the assignment is held in groups. Success achieved as a result of cooperation depends on the regular and active mental work of student at the lesson. One way to adapt materials is to remake reading texts and grade the language accordingly for determination of gaps between group of people. In an ideal world where a teacher has all the time among the world to prepare their lessons which may be apparent solution. However, the reality is that this kind of adaptation is too time consuming. Kasimova G. and Ismonova T. stated that another trouble that can arise with this type of adaptation is that it can be tricky announce non-identical texts to unsimilar students. It is necessary to feel personal, responsibility and to develop a system of encouraging it. Due to working within a group learners are given some qualities.

1. Mutual information exchange is done regularly.
2. To provide gathering and sharing of ideas and opinions.

Working in a group is better than working individually. As a result of cooperation the activity of weak can increase due to the influence of active in the group.

As a result of effective application of the method, following can be achieved.

1. Feelings of trust and respect for each other are increased.
2. Ability to speak justify and defend one's opinion is increased
3. Skills for learning and working are developed

Results and discussions

More hands make for lighter work. It emphasizes the importance of teamwork and cooperation. It means how a difficult task can be easier, quicker when people aid. This proverb speak to the prospective groups have to be more fruitful, ingenious and inspired than individuals. Appropriately, ordered group proposals fortify skills that are applicable to both group and individuals work, including the ability breaking tough

tasks into parts and steps. Scheduling. Enhance comprehensive through debates and clarification. Give and receive feedbacks on face-to-face in order to improve interaction skills among group of people. (Astina, 1993, What matters in college?). There are some working on people themselves can sometimes feel more uncomplicated. It can be productive, people can work on the project themselves time and people are charge of the whole action. On the basis of engaging in group work, though it is forced impose human by his or her teacher or boss or it is a study group which is school or may be some kind of college or institute. People plan their friends, group can be in aiding people functional to improve knowledge and apprehension of issues. It can be considered one of the widely used interactive methods. Moreover, Tinton claimed that this method provides learners to attend actively in the lesson and also give a choice to participate in the discussion. Mainly, it teaches to appreciate the opinions of others, learners get used to distributing tasks clearly between them by working in groups. When working with a group, they have the opportunity to actively participate in the lesson, to learn some knowledge from each other and to compare different points of view. Hackman stated that collaborative action of learners is organized which helps to activate the learning process, to develop empathy and communicativeness. In the process of cooperative performance of the task, learners are motivated to discuss the opinions expressed by their peers. Learners ask each other questions, and as a result, they also learn to formulate questions clearly. Moreover, they learn to listen carefully to each other in order to reason and understand the answers. When working in a group, learners ask for help when they needed and learn to help others. Talented learners can show off their talents without fear of being blamed. Learners with average ability or timid character will have the opportunity to demonstrate their knowledge and skills. Working in a group relieves them of stress. Working in a group changes the attitude towards others and also provides a transition from me and them to us. Furthermore, it allows to them feel part of the group.

Conclusion

To sum up, working in a group helps to improve skills such as ability to effectively convey or share ideas and feeling cooperation and leadership. Essentially, it makes the work more absorbing, more motivating. Working in a group is absolutely more favorable than working solitary. People should work jointly and mix themselves into the community. Working in a group enhances decision making in an organization as working as an individuals in which case there are data insufficiency. The resources of the organization are shared and this play down the costs. Group work gives students the chance to catch in process skills critical for processing information, and evaluating and assessing brainstorming as well as management skills, through the use of role within groups and evaluation skills involved in assessing options about their group's last answer. Group work helps individuals to improve by honesty motivation and adapt to the exchange social context and aids improve conduct or attitude. Taking into account the strengths and weaknesses of learners, the work should be organized in such a way that each student can influence the results of the group work. Moreover, their roles should be alternated when performing different tasks.

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